

**ASSOCIATED APPLICANCE OF ARTROSCOPIC DEBRIDEMENT AND
PROXIMAL FIBULAR OSTEOTOMY AT THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS
WITH DEFORMIC ARTRITIS OF KNEE**

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Objective

Arthroscopic diagnosis and treatment - determining the functional status of the joint, debridement of degenerative-dystrophic tissue, cleaning of chondromalacia foci, tunneling operations have solved important problems of advanced orthopedics [2].

According to scientists, after the operation of proximal fibular osteotomy (PFO) in deformed osteoarthritis of the knee, due to the weakening of the external components of the knee joint changes the balance of the joint and the mechanism of redistribution of load on the outer and inner plateaus [1].

However, the above-mentioned degenerative-dystrophic changes in the knee joint and debridement aimed at restoring the biomechanical axis of the lower limb and the combined use of proximal fibular osteotomies are emerging.

Materials and investigation methods. In our study, we included 152 patients with grade I-II-III deformity arthritis and varus deformity of the knee joint aged 35-80 years treated in the Department of Sports Trauma of the Republican Specialized Scientific-Practical Medical Center for Traumatology and Orthopedics and the traumatology department of Bukhara branch of the Republican Scientific Center of Emergency Care between 2018 and 2020. (1961). All patients were divided into 2 groups and long-term postoperative outcomes were studied. Group I (control) consisted of 131 patients, of which 115 were women and 18 were men. Patients in this group underwent debridement of joint surfaces. Group II (basic) consisted of 19 patients, including 15 women, 4 men. This group of patients underwent joint debridement and PFO, the surgical procedure developed in our clinic and a

utility model patent (FAP 35926) was obtained .Patients underwent knee debridement and PFO surgeries performed according to standard techniques. Surgical procedures were performed under arthroscopy.Surgical procedures were performed under arthroscopy.The analysis of the obtained results was evaluated on the basis of indicators of KSS (Knee Society Scores) scale.

Results. The results of the surgery were reviewed at 3, 6, 12 months (short-term) and 1 year (long-term) after the operation.Evaluation of the obtained results was carried out on the basis of anterior and lateral projection radiographic data and KSS scale.The results of surgical procedures performed in 133 patients of control groups and 19 patients of the basic groups with osteoarthritis of the knee joint were evaluated based on the analysis of clinical and functional indicators of the KSS scale. From the clinical indicators, the intensity of pain syndrome was assessed on the basis of "mild pain and moderate pain" criteria and showed a significant decrease in the number of patients in the control group after arthroscopic debridement + PFO procedures performed in the basic group of patients, in the control group, "mild pain" increased by 14.3%, "moderate pain" decreased by 46%, and in the basic group of patients, "mild pain" decreased by 5%, and "moderate pain" decreased by 63%.

In summary,, it was found that among all joints, the occurrence of deforming arthrosis of the knee joint was predominant.An analysis of the results obtained in the basic and control group patients showed that the complex application of knee joint derivative and PFO surgeries significantly improved the percentage of positive outcomes.In patients with deforming osteoarthritis of the knee joint, the KSS scale allows adequate evaluation of the results of clinical and functional examination after surgery.

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2.Wang X. et al. / Proximal fibular osteotomy: a new surgery for pain relief and improvement of joint function in patients with knee osteoarthritis. // Journal of International Medical Research, 2017;45(1):282.

